

Milestone:

MS23 - Annual workshop on data quality: data linkage - 1 of 2

Lead Participant:

HRI

Author:

Due:

June 2024

Date Of Completion:

06/06/2024

Means of Verification

Notes of the workshop planned and held on 2024-06-06 from 13:00-16:00 CEST. These notes are at <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1sSoGOcEgAHB-r1GhL8jSVM1ZqtC4G5leBH2cpsmEYCI/edit?usp=sharing>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

Planning and workshop hosting was performed by Rob Hooft with help of Jeroen Belien (Task leads T6.3) .

The workshop had invitees from the whole project, focusing on WP6 but attendance included also representatives from Pillar I and Pillar III.

External speakers were Dieter Hahn (AIT) on PPRL and Konstantin HYPPONEN and Szymon BIELECKI (both DG-CNECT) on EHDS.

Next action steps

Data linkage is an issue that needs to be solved in each of the member countries separately, compatible with national legal constraints.

T6.3 should probably work on SOPs to help countries make the right choices, documenting the options and the way to choose between them.

Workshops between Pillar I and Pillar II on legal and governance recommendations for the technical infrastructure will also help this task forward.

